

Surfactant mediated nanoparticle aggregation and its application for SERS studies^ψ

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Silver nanoparticle formation has been examined in different micellar media. These nanosize particles can produce linear aggregates with suitable electrolyte. The linear aggregates in micellar media provide information for several biologically active molecules while used as surface enhanced Raman scattering (SERS) substrate.

The Raman enhancement effect by molecules adsorbed onto the silver surface has been the subject of considerable interest. These studies generally exploit the high sensitivity of surface enhanced Raman scattering (SERS) and the quenching of fluorescence caused by adsorption of molecules on metallic surfaces¹. The theory of enhancement of signal may be due to electromagnetic or charge-transfer aspects². Keeping an eye to the sensitivity and reproducibility aspects, herein is reported SERS spectra for several visible-transparent biologically active molecules adsorbed on the electrolyte-induced and micelle-mediated linearly aggregated silver colloid as an alternative and useful colloid system.

Results and Discussion

Since the discovery of SERS, exhaustive efforts have been devoted in a number of laboratories towards the development of practical substrates to investigate and utilise the SERS effect^{1,2}. The cause and theory of SERS is still a subject of much debate. However, it is presumed that the oscillating electric field of a light beam induces an oscillating dipole in a colloidal metal particle. This oscillating dipole can be thought of as the free conduction electrons oscillating up and down in phase with the oscillating field. If the natural frequency of oscillation of the conduction electrons (the plasma oscillation frequency) matches the frequency of the light, the plasma oscillation is in resonance with the light, and the induced dipole becomes practically large.

Fig. 1 shows the polarisation of two colloidal particles which are close together in an aggregate. The minus sign at

Fig. 1. Polarisation of two colloidal particles which are close together in an aggregate.

the top of each particle indicates that the oscillating field of the incoming light is up, displacing electrons to the top of the particles and leaving positive charges at the bottom of the particles. The induced dipoles radiate their own electric field lines as shown in the diagram. This so-called secondary field also oscillates at the frequency of the light, and it is the molecules adsorbed at the surface of the particles which Raman scatter their secondary field giving rise to the SERS effect. It may be noticed that the secondary field is particularly big where the spheres are almost touching because of the close proximity of the positive charges in one particle and the negative charges in the other, and most of the SERS comes from molecules near the point of contact. Theoretical prediction tells that the intensity of SERS depends critically on the distance between the two particles³ (especially at very small distance apart).

Results of this effort have included works with silver colloid particles in micelle for the first time.

The aggregation of silver nanoparticle was studied by visible spectrophotometry in the presence of MgCl₂ (0.1%). The aggregation step is a very important step to observe SERS enhancement. The silver hydrosol caused an

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adsorption band to appear at 400 nm and after the aggregation of the sol particles a new band appeared at ~630 nm region along with that of the original band of the hydrosol. The appearance of the new band becomes visible at the expense of the 400 nm band. To cause the new band to appear at 630 nm region the peak height of the original 400 nm band diminishes as a matter of compensation. Thus the integrated adsorption remains constant. This sort of aggregation has been found to be an obligatory step for SERS measurement¹. TEM studies revealed the linear assemblies of silver particles⁴.

Tetracaine, a well known drug and methyl viologen, a herbicide have been considered for SERS studies. Ethanolic solution of tetracaine and aqueous solution of methyl viologen were used to keep the final concentration of the compounds in the range of $10^{-7}M$ in the aggregated silver sol solution. The most important Raman bands which are found to be enhanced appeared at 1600, 1460, 1350, 1275, 1160, 1120, 850 cm^{-1} for tetracaine and at 1650, 1820, 1320, 1200 and 850 cm^{-1} and for methyl viologen.

The effects of surfactants were, however, a bit peculiar⁵. Unlike the cationic surfactants, nonionic and anionic surfactants have been found to be suitable for stabilisation of linear colloidal aggregates of silver and a further enhancement of SERS signal intensities were noticed. Possibly cationic surfactants such as CTAB (cetyltrimethylammonium bromide) was adsorbed more strongly onto the silver surface than nonionic and anionic surfactants. This may be attributed to the presence of strong ligand anion, in this case Br^- of CTAB. They are therefore chemisorbed; whereas perhaps nonionic and anionic surfactants without such ligand anion go to the surface of the particles and physisorbed, because they are 'squeezed out' from the solution by the network of water molecules trying to maximise their hydrogen bonding. May be the adsorption of cationic surfactants is strong enough to force the colloid aggregates slightly apart increasing the distance between the particles, and therefore seriously reducing SERS. It is concluded that the linear aggregates of silver in anionic or nonionic surfactant is a well suited substrate for obtaining better enhanced SERS signal intensities. It would be interesting to look at electron micrographs of aggregated silver colloids treated with CTAB, Triton X-100 chemically known as poly(oxyethylene) isooctylphenyl ether and SDS (sodium dodecyl sulfate), to

see if there is evidence of a gap between the particles treated with CTAB. Gold colloids may be a better choice as they give much better images with better contrast than silver colloids.

Another test of the above idea would be to try to obtain cationic surfactant without a strong ligand anion such as Br^- or Cl^- . On the otherhand, BF_4^- , PF_6^- , ClO_4^- or even NO_3^- would be the possibilities. Thus this leaves a scope for future studies.

Experimental

The yellow silver hydrosol ($\lambda_{max} = 400$ nm) generated from $10^{-3}M$ $AgNO_3$ and $10^{-2}M$ $NaBH_4$ solutions were effectively aggregated linearly in a nonionic surfactant TX-100 or anionic surfactant SDS medium with $MgCl_2$ (0.1%) solution, which showed an additional new adsorption band at ~630 nm along with the original band of the hydrosol³.

The stable aggregated aqueous solution of silver colloid in surfactant medium (1 ml) was used to obtain SERS spectra in a 1 cm quartz cuvette mixing the colloid with 5 μl aqueous or ethanolic solution ($\sim 10^{-4}M$; 5 μl) of tetracaine, methyl viologen, etc. SERS spectra were acquired with a SA, Inc. HR-320 spectrograph equipped with Princeton instrument charge-coupled device (RE-ICCD). Measurements were done with Kr laser (200 mW) using 30 nm entrance slit.

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References

1. J. A. Creighton, C. G. Blatchford and M. G. Albrecht, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 2*, 1979, 790.
2. N. -S. Lee, Y. -Z. Hsieh, M. D. Morris and L. M. Schopfer, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **109**, 1358.
3. J. I. Gersten, N. Liver and A. Nitzan, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1984, **111**, 449.
4. T. Pal, N. R. Jana and T. Sau, *Curr. Sci.*, 1997, **73**, 906; A. Pal and T. Pal, *J. Raman Spectrosc.*, 1999, **30**, 1999.
5. T. Pal, N. R. Jana and T. Sau, *Langmuir*, 1997, **13**, 1481; T. Pal, T. Sau and N. R. Jana, *J. Phys. Chem. (B)*, 1999, **103**, 115; T. Pal and N. R. Jana, *Langmuir*, 1999, **15**, 3458.